

**THE PORTFOLIO AS A FORMATIVE DEVICE IN SUPERVISED INTERNSHIP: AN
EXPERIENCE REPORT**

LE PORTFOLIO COMME DISPOSITIF DE FORMATION AU STAGE SUPERVISÉ : UN RAPPORT
D'EXPÉRIENCE

O PORTFÓLIO COMO DISPOSITIVO FORMATIVO NO ESTÁGIO SUPERVISIONADO: UM
RELATO DE EXPERIÊNCIA

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Abstract

During the supervised internship, the future teacher has the opportunity to experience school daily life. In teacher training programs at the State University of Campinas (Unicamp), the majority of students carry out two supervised internships at the Faculty of Education (FE) and another two at institutes linked to their respective degree programs. The present article aims to present an experience report on the construction of a reflective portfolio as a training device during an internship course at FE-Unicamp, taught by the second and third authors of this article, with the aim of enabling reflections on the teaching experiences of students in the training process, with a view to the continuous exercise of action-reflection-action, practice-theory-practice. The experience presented refers to the work developed by the first author, a student on the Geography Degree course, in elementary school, in a 3rd year class at a peripheral and urban public school in the city of Campinas, São Paulo. The portfolio was composed of: narratives, letters to teachers who were part of their school training, teaching project, contributions from students from other degrees (in discussion circles held in classes at the university) and a narrative final reflection. Finally, we reinforce the power of the reflective portfolio as an essential training device to strengthen teaching training and practice.

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Key-words: Initial teacher education; Portfolio; Supervised internship.

Résumé

Au cours de stage supervisé, le futur.e enseignant.e a l'opportunité de vivre la vie quotidienne de l'école. Dans les programmes de formation d'enseignant.e.s de l'Université d'État de Campinas (Unicamp), la majorité des étudiant.e.s effectuent deux stages obligatoires supervisés à la Faculté d'Éducation (FE) et deux autres dans des instituts liés à leurs programmes respectifs. Le présent travail vise à présenter un rapport d'expérience sur la construction d'un portfolio réflexif comme dispositif de formation lors d'une discipline de stage à FE-Unicamp, enseigné par les deuxième et troisième auteurs de cet article, dans le but de permettre une réflexion sur les expériences d'enseignement des étudiants dans le processus de formation, en vue de l'exercice continu de l'action-réflexion-action, de la pratique-théorie-pratique. L'expérience présentée fait référence au travail développé par le premier auteur, étudiant en licence de géographie, à l'école primaire, dans une classe de 3^{ème} année d'une école publique périphérique et urbaine de la ville de Campinas, São Paulo. Le portfolio était composé de : récits, lettres aux enseignants qui faisaient partie de leur formation scolaire, projet pédagogique, contributions d'étudiants d'autres diplômes (dans des cercles de discussion organisés dans les classes de l'université) et une réflexion finale narrative. Enfin, nous renforçons la puissance du portfolio réflexif en tant que dispositif de formation essentiel pour renforcer la formation et la pratique pédagogiques.

Mots-clés: Formation initiale des enseignants; Portfolio; Stage supervise.

Resumo

Durante o estágio supervisionado, o(a) futuro(a) professor(a) tem a oportunidade de experienciar o cotidiano escolar. Nos cursos de formação docente da Universidade Estadual de Campinas (Unicamp), os(as) estudantes realizam, em sua maioria, dois estágios supervisionados obrigatórios na Faculdade de Educação (FE) e outros dois nos institutos vinculados aos seus respectivos cursos de licenciatura. O presente trabalho visa a apresentar um relato de experiência na construção de um portfólio reflexivo como dispositivo formativo durante uma disciplina de estágio da FE-Unicamp, ministrada pelas segunda e terceira autoras deste artigo, com o objetivo de possibilitar reflexões acerca das experiências docentes de estudantes em processo de formação, tendo em vista o exercício contínuo de ação-reflexão-ação, prática-teoria-prática. A experiência apresentada refere-se ao trabalho desenvolvido pelo primeiro autor, estudante do curso de Licenciatura em Geografia, no ensino fundamental anos iniciais, em uma turma de 3^º ano de uma escola pública periférica e urbana da cidade de Campinas, São Paulo. O portfólio foi composto por: narrativas, cartas para os(as) professores(as) que fizeram parte de sua formação escolar, projeto de ensino, contribuições de estudantes de outras licenciaturas (nas rodas de discussão realizadas nas aulas na universidade) e uma narrativa reflexiva final. Por fim, reforçamos a potência do portfólio reflexivo como um dispositivo formativo essencial para fortalecer a formação e a prática docente.

Palavras-chave: Formação inicial de professores(as); Portfólio; Estágio supervisionado.

Introduction

In teacher training programs, the internship plays a fundamental role in preparing students for their future professional insertion. The student teachers approach school and professional daily life with a new perspective, that of the future teacher (Cyrino; Benites; Souza Neto, 2015).

For this new perspective to contribute to a training focused on the profession (Nóvoa, 2009) and avoid that some aspects of teaching are reproduced without critical reflection (Tardif; Raymond, 2000), we think it is essential that students are challenged to observe what they do, to share their experiences with their colleagues, and reflect on other possibilities of action in the different contexts in which they are inserted.

Despite their weaknesses, Brazilian policies on teacher education contribute in this direction, recognizing that “initial teacher education should be organized to ensure initial professional socialization” (Brasil, 2024, p. 2, our translation).

This regulation indicates that the program record and the student teachers' experiences, among other factors, must be considered when performing this activity to address the supervised curricular internship.

Thus, we suggest the “portfolio or equivalent follow-up resource, where observations are noted, as well as critical reflections, didactic planning, and experience reports, among other evidence of the undergraduate's learning required for teaching” (Brasil, 2024, p. 6, our translation).

In this sense, when we understand that “teaching requires critical reflection on practice” (Freire, 1996, p. 38, our translation), in initial training, recording and narrative writing can “contribute to the deepening of theories on the epistemology of practice, adding another look at the problematization of knowledge produced by teachers and other school professionals in the context of pedagogical work” (Prado, 2013, p. 152, our translation).

More than narrating, recording and reflecting, sharing experiences among students in the internship helps foster self-recognition in the relationship with others, through a complex process of reciprocal professional constitution, as “through others we constitute ourselves” (Vygotsky, 2000, p. 24, our translation).

In the Universidade Estadual de Campinas's (Unicamp) teacher training programs, students typically complete two mandatory supervised internships at the Faculty of Education (FE-Unicamp) and two additional internships at institutes affiliated with their respective teacher training programs. We consider it relevant to highlight that, since 2008, FE-Unicamp has adopted a proposal for configuring interdisciplinary classes in supervised

internships, which comprise students from various areas of knowledge. According to Ayoub and Prado (2013, p. 398, our translation),

from the collective work between subject areas in an interdisciplinary perspective, the knowledge of teacher training [...] is re-signified, producing new meanings regarding the various professional knowledge necessary for teacher training. This dialogue between different fields of knowledge generates the possibility for more integrated thematic treatments, complicating their understanding and highlighting opportunities for intertwining the knowledge of each area of undergraduate training to enhance understanding of the themes developed in school and other educational settings.

We developed this work within the context of a dialogue between different areas and perspectives, characterized as an experience report by the first author, an student teacher in Geography, who built a reflective portfolio. This portfolio was proposed as a training tool in a supervised internship subject of the Faculty of Education of Unicamp, taught by the second and third authors. The fourth author is also a professor at Unicamp, where they work in teacher training at the Institute of Geosciences, and advised the first author's term paper, which is based on the reflective portfolio under analysis.

Next, we present the path taken in this process, approach the role of writing and the portfolio in the teacher training process, and introduce the portfolio and its possibilities for reflection.

Methodology

As mentioned above, the experience reported here refers to work developed in a supervised internship at the Unicamp Faculty of Education. The subject "Supervised Internship II" was offered in the second semester of 2023, attracting around 20 students from teacher training programs in various fields, including Geography, Music, Dance, Physical Education, Physics, and Mathematics. During the classes, it was proposed that students produce a training portfolio to track their progress, facilitating reflections on their experiences through the continuous cycle of action-reflection-action, practice-theory-practice (Freire, 1996).

Students were encouraged to produce reflective narratives, letters, and other written texts throughout the course. Thus, they should select those that made the most sense to compose the tool. The format was free, and each student organized their material however they preferred. Some wrote in notebooks or on blank sheets of paper, while others preferred digital documents. During the classes, the students shared their writings and experiences from the internship, which informed their reflections on the pedagogical practice.

In this report, we present excerpts from the portfolio⁵ of the first author, a Geography student. He completed his internship in the third year of elementary school in a public school in Campinas, SP.

His portfolio consisted of narratives, letters to teachers who were part of his school education, teaching projects, contributions from students of other degrees (in the discussion rounds held in classes at the University), and a final reflective narrative. This writing practice later resulted in a term paper project, as we explained earlier.

After discussing the role of writing and the portfolio in the training process, we will share excerpts from the first author's experiences, as recorded in his portfolio, along with an analysis of this teaching experience. These analyses will highlight teaching experiences with school students and offer reflections on the development of teaching. It is essential to note that, in certain instances of writing, readers may encounter the first-person singular, as these are excerpts narrated by the first author in their portfolio.

The role of portfolio writing and production in the training process

Writing changes from place to place (Kleiman, 2010). Throughout the student trajectory, we write to be evaluated by someone. During the early years of elementary school, we learn to write with numerous tools developed over the centuries. We learn letters, phonemes, syllables, words, and phrases. In the final years of elementary school, we understand prayer, direct object, indirect object, adverbial adjunct, article, and the

⁵ The excerpts underwent a revision process when necessary, with minor spelling and grammatical adjustments.

other grammatical categories that help us write the texts of this moment in life and, gradually, make us build more elaborate texts to pass, whether in a college entrance exam or a job interview. However, we usually don't write to reflect, even creatively.

In this context, when we consider initial teacher training, writing becomes an important element in the construction of teaching identity, as "writing is a possibility for the trainee to transform their action" (Tartuce; Davis; Almeida, 2021, p. 11, our translation).

As we have already indicated in the introduction, the portfolio is a valuable training tool for writing. Sá-Chaves (2007) defines a portfolio as a cluster of reports and experiences within a specific temporal and physical context that have a reflective and interpersonal intention, contributing to the construction of the teaching identity.

Writing, by itself, is always a solitary and individual action. However, when considering the production of portfolios with the intention of training teachers who can reflect on their actions, such writing must be shared and, in this movement, "intensify the process of remembrance, to put into dialogue apparently solitary and individual experiences, but which are shared by all of us, since they are inevitably anchored in the social relations that constitute us as human beings" (Ayoub, 2021, p. 43, our translation).

Thus, this process of sharing the writings in the portfolio among the student teachers can lead to the development of action research, in which their doubts, experiences, anxieties, and concerns are exposed. This meeting space becomes a moment for producing teaching knowledge, and the anxieties noted in each person's experiences sometimes converge, mobilizing a joint effort to construct strategies for addressing such problems.

Zabalza (2004) indicates that the diary is crucial for expressing experiences and emotions. Writing the portfolio fulfills the function of a diary very well, allowing for the reconstruction of many lived experiences and, thus, the possibility of identifying gaps that are not apparent and, even less, analyzed during the experience. In this context, the proposals of Sá-Chaves (2007) and Zabalza (2004) converge:

[...] the diary fulfills an essential role as an element of expression of experiences and emotions. Writing about oneself brings with it the realization of the processes to which we have previously referred: the experience is rationalized by writing it (what had an emotional or affective nature becomes, in addition, cognitive nature, thus becoming more manageable), reconstructs the experience,

therefore giving the possibility of distancing and analysis, and, if desired, facilitates the possibility of socializing the experience, sharing it with a personal advisor or a group of colleagues (Zabalza, 2004, p. 18, our translation).

Like diaries, portfolios do not serve as a punctual and final evaluation since “they are continuously (re)elaborated in the action and shared to collect, in good time, other ways of seeing and interpreting that facilitate to the student an expansion and diversification of their gaze” (Sá-Chaves, 2007, p. 15, our translation).

We then move on to the reflective movement present in the portfolio prepared by the first author regarding the supervised internship, sharing and dialoguing with some of their writings in this training tool.

The portfolio and its possibilities for reflection

The cycle of action-reflection-action is indispensable for pedagogical praxis, which, in turn, is linked to practice-theory-practice (Freire, 1996). When students of teacher training programs come into contact with the school and experience teaching, it is essential that they record, think, and share what they have experienced so that, later, in the face of new educational situations, they can transform their actions, both as trainees and, in the future, as teachers.

The portfolio offers this possibility to the extent that, by storing the writings and experiences of the practice, the trainee can revisit them and, with a new perspective, reevaluate their actions and reflections.

The student teacher sought a common thread when beginning to write the portfolio:

my initial idea is to write letters (apparently the teacher seems to have a lot of affection for this type of writing) to the teachers who composed my trajectory, first to thank and then to tell the experiences lived and, finally, to try to understand how many teachers formed this student who is on the path to become a teacher (Bairo, 2023, p. 1, our translation).

When choosing letters as a textual genre with a strong affective characteristic, the trainee also recognizes the influences of their former teachers on their professional constitution. This idea is consistently emphasized in Tardif's (2002) writings, which suggest that teaching work is strongly linked to emotions.

We are constantly affected by the relationships we form in school, whether with our teachers, colleagues, or even with managers and employees within the school institution. In the case of relationships with teachers, we cite an instigating work that refers us to the power of these encounters and/or disagreements: “Meu professor inesquecível: ensinamentos e aprendizados contados por alguns dos nossos melhores escritores” (Abramovich, 1997).

We continue the dialogue through the narrated experiences, which are now more closely connected to the students. We will then reflect on the development of our teaching.

Teaching experiences with school students

During the internship experience, the Geography student experienced the world through collective writing with the students:

there was a collective text production, with the retelling of the short story "The Princess and the Frog," and the teacher served as the class scribe. What is the purpose of this writing? First, it serves as an example for the students' future productions, as there is a trajectory before writing as an individual activity for each one. Second, to demonstrate punctuation, along with the organization of paragraphs, allied to the cohesion and coherence of the story. The teacher explained that to reach this point, the story must be firmly fixed in their heads, because when the narrative is well-embedded, attention becomes more focused on punctuation and the other characteristics of the text (Bairo, 2023, p. 48, our translation).

The elaboration of this joint writing, mentioned in the excerpt above, and the explanation of the polyvalent teacher show the importance of having a clear objective in the proposed activities. Pinheiro (2011, p. 228, our translation) assumes that: “[...] in a group writing work, the complementarity of skills, knowledge, individual efforts of opinions and points of view, and a greater ability to generate more viable alternatives for solving problems can occur”. That is, in the joint production of texts, students understand what they are writing, compare their ideas, and, at the same time, manage to reflect on what they are producing. This perspective of collective and collaborative work can favor significant learning.

The writing process, especially reflective writing about lived experiences, was vital for constructing the educator in training, the student teacher. We begin by highlighting that the excerpt reveals only one of the many entertaining and educational moments he

could reflect on, reorder, and relive while rereading the portfolio he built over a semester. The internship experience, which occurred once or twice a week, provided significant insights, and the act of writing on the same day, with a recent memory, allowed us to reconstruct processes that had escaped us throughout the day.

When developing an action proposal in the context of the initial years of elementary school (as proposed by the internship subject), the student teacher developed a practice that proposed to change the usual configuration of the room, so that students could learn less rigidly and linearly:

i asked the students to organize themselves in the room by arranging their desks in a U shape. I said good morning and began discussing what I had already done with the class, such as the dynamics of the exchange of places at the beginning when I entered. Then, I shifted the subject to the theme of “territory”. I put a large word, “TERRITORY,” on the blackboard and asked everyone what they knew. I explained what it was and how our body is also a territory. And I approached, very lightly, the question of scale, bodily speaking, from houses, to neighborhoods, to cities, states, countries, and continents, conceptualizing what territory was (Bairo, 2023, p. 70).

Its first movement began with the intention of creating a class that could be experienced differently by reconfiguring a space commonly found in students' daily lives. This alternative approach to spatially configuring the classroom would enable the expansion of the environment and move away from the traditional model of desk organization, characterized by rows and columns, prevalent in many school institutions. It would allow all students to help build that class, especially when the trainee brought brown paper and placed it in the middle of the room to draw their bodies.

With the word “territory” on the blackboard, he asked the students to explain their previous knowledge. Paulo Freire, in "Pedagogia do oprimido" (Freire, 2019), emphasizes the importance of considering students' knowledge. The student teacher sought to understand this movement, acknowledging each individual's existing conceptions and building upon them to create new knowledge. After sharing this information, he continued the class with some considerations that sought to bring the Geography of the Elementary I class closer.

Based on this, I explained the purpose of the task so they would work in pairs with colleagues with whom they had no affinity (perhaps it was my first mistake). I explained that they would draw themselves life-size and then assign three characteristics of the partner they liked or admired. In detail, they would do all this on brown paper, that is, on the floor, and work on the total space existing in the classroom (Bairo, 2023, p. 71, our translation).

Throughout the day, as an student teacher in a class with almost 30 students, he got the impression that the proposed activity was very tiring and full of unpredictability, which, from his perspective, were mistakes of a teacher in initial training. However, other indications made him think it was possible to mobilize some learning with the students.

Subsequently, we worked with mathematics, and I was phagocytosed entirely by the students of classroom 3rd A. And the lens that hits me at this moment is one that is not very familiar to me as a teacher because, as much as I try to dialogue with all my “teachings” or attempts at teaching Geography, in some cases, as in basic mathematics, it is difficult. Of course, it is possible to merge the two areas; I can even outline some strategies for this, but when the content is very basic, the task is more arduous than it seems (Bairo, 2023, p. 38, our translation).

A student called me to ask about the activity, and soon after I explained it, she asked why it was so hot. Here was my moment to shine as a geographer. At this moment, I explained superficially what the greenhouse effect, the ozone layer, and the entry of solar rays into Planet Earth are, and it was fun (Bairo, 2023, p. 39, our translation).

These two excerpts illustrate how school knowledge can be presented and mediated in various ways within daily school life, as well as the challenges that arise from this. Teachers deal with a more planned dynamic when intentionally seeking to establish relationships and approximations between knowledge from different areas, for example, or create didactic strategies to teach specific content. On the other hand, when teachers understand that there are opportunities to teach that escape the strictly planned, they can develop the ability to perceive other situations in which it is possible to work school knowledge more spontaneously, taking advantage of the epistemological curiosity of children, of human beings, as Freire (1996) teaches us.

Reflections on development in teaching

The letters written to the teachers highlight the influence of these professionals on the trainee's training and teaching practice and on how their educational actions reverberate to the present day, both as a trainee and as a future Geography teacher. According to Brait and collaborators (2010), the relationship between teacher and student is based on empathic connections from the teacher, which provide a two-way street, in

which one learns and teaches simultaneously. From this perspective, it is essential to acknowledge the individuals who helped shape this path of teaching.

To a chemistry teacher, the student teacher wrote that

it is impossible to be Vygotskian all the time, and with a room of 40 students, but it is possible to recognize the theory that guides their actions in the face of everyday knowledge. It is precisely at this point that Geography is present in this discussion. Ultimately, geography is present at all times and everywhere, as everything occurs within a specific space and through relationships (Bairo, 2023, p. 103, our translation).

This fragment raises a central question concerning the nature of teaching knowledge, as discussed by Tardif (2002), which goes far beyond the domain of academic content. This knowledge combines personal and professional experiences, the pedagogical strategies developed, and the theories underlying daily teaching practices. However, as mentioned in the fragment above, reality can significantly diverge from classroom education theories, especially when facing large classes and, consequently, a diverse range of needs.

Such a contrast between theory and practice is a common experience in teaching, but far from being a problem. On the contrary, it reinforces the importance of “teaching knowledge” as a dynamic synthesis. Within a classroom, it is necessary to constantly adjust the actions according to the demands of the collective of students. Even if it is impossible to follow a specific educational theory all the time, we must be guided by conceptions that guide and inform our pedagogical decisions. Thus, teaching practice becomes an act of continuous reflection, intertwining theory and practice and creating new possibilities for pedagogical action.

In the sphere of Geography, this discussion is deeply linked to everyday life and school space, considering that Geography happens constantly, in all places and times, as human and spatial relationships come to the fore. It reinforces the idea that Geography teachers teach geographical concepts and help students critically and reflectively interpret and understand the world in which they are a part. Therefore, the teaching knowledge related to Geography integrates the ability to read, understand, and interact with the space in which students live, recognizing Geography as a living and everyday science.

Ultimately, the reflection on "teaching knowledge" reveals that teacher training is not only a matter of absorbing theories and "applying" them mechanically, but of developing a sensitivity to navigate between different knowledge - academic, personal, and practical - and make them meet in a meaningful way in the classroom. Thus, the challenge is not to be "Vygotskian" all the time, but to know how to use different theories in a flexible and contextualized way, according to the needs and specificities of each teaching situation.

Final Remarks

We arrive at this experience report's final remarks, reinforcing the reflective portfolio's power as a vital training tool to enhance teacher training and practice. In the words of Idália Sá-Chaves in an interview conducted by Nadal Gomes, Pessate and Gomes (2004, p. 13; emphasis added), "the reflexive *portfolio* is, fundamentally, a training strategy that, through the supervisory relationship established between trainee and trainer, allows **sustained learning**".

We also emphasize that sharing the writings in the portfolio among the classmates of the internship class can further favor the reflective processes about the teaching experiences lived in the different contexts of the supervised internship.

Specifically, in our subject, the students shared in moments reserved for these dialogues, fostered by questions the teachers proposed so that they could focus the reflection on points of teaching that we considered important.

Thus, there remains the constant challenge of exploring the full potential of this training tool to further strengthen the dialogical processes in teacher training.

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